

ISic1365

I.Sicily inscription 1365

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140870

1. [Π]ρι[μ]ο[γ]ένη [ς]
2. έτελεύτη-
3. σεν, ζήσας
4. έτη ο, και έν-
5. θάδε κίται.
6. □c ²⁶χρ(ιστό)ς²⁶
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492979

EDCS 39101745

PHI 140870

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin.

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